

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SHIN****FIRST NAME: WOOSEOK****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 6%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

List your five key concepts with the page number in the text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Using Zotero software
2. Writing essay principles (Cleenewerch and Gulma 2024, 6-14)
3. Technical Aspects: punctuations, American vs. British English, Chicago Manual of Style, and Latin abbreviations and expressions (Cleenewerch and Gulma 2024, 15-23, 24-32, 43-57, 58-64)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerch and Gulma 2024, 33-39)
5. Style guide consideration (Cleenewerch and Gulma 2024, 40-42)

ACA-401D COURSEPACK: PERIOD 1

1) INTRODUCTION

I am wholeheartedly grateful and thrilled to begin pursuing my Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in international law and treaty at EUCLID University, which would be an extension of my research career as a young international dispute resolution scholar. Given my engagement in international investment law practice, such experiences would vastly expand the degree of insights into relevant topics and effectively assist in acutely navigating research.

This ACA-401D coursepack is invaluable for improving my academic writing as I have yet to be exposed to an opportunity to establish the fundamental technical aspects of drafting a research paper. Misuse of Latin dictum, punctuation, or other technical errors would leave an impression to the readers that the author has not carefully proofread his paper, which should be prevented. As a self-reflection, I must confess that I have been unable to stand out as a careful writer without such mistakes. Thus, I extend my gratitude for this opportunity to gain experience about these essential fundamentals and knowledge to the esteemed authors of this book.

Furthermore, it is important to note that using Zotero appears extremely useful for me in reducing the unnecessary burden of spending long hours double-checking the references and navigating the relevant sources promptly. Throughout the first few months of 2025, I aim to familiarize myself with using Zotero to advance the promptness of writing and invest my capacity more appropriately.

Turning to the current coursepack written by Prof. Cleenewerck and Prof. Gulma (the “authors”), this research paper provides five main points: essay writing principles, technical aspects, Plagiarism, and style guide considerations. The section below will summarize the essential elements of the above main points. The following section will address my findings and opinions on the information provided in the ACA-401D coursepack.

2) WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

a) Principles of Essay Writing

The first chapter of the coursepack addresses the primary principles of producing a good essay, including some concrete rules of thumb for writing paper (Cleenewerch and Gulma 2024, 6). The initial steps preceding any other steps to write is undoubtedly researching the relevant topic to expand the degree of understanding the issues present in specific fields, which will subsequently create responses to the questions such as what materials are needed to understand which topic (Cleenewerch and Gulma 2024, 8). It is recommended that the research should “*keep the topic or question of the essay clearly in mind and note [them as] sound evidence to support your argument*” (Cleenewerch and Gulma 2024, 9). Taking notes or comments while reading has been one of the most significant recommendations, I have adopted to enhance efficiency and maintain the sharpness of the analysis, resulting in more opportunities in my career as a legal professional.

Apart from essential notes on referencing and editing the essay, the coursepack provides valuable rules of thumb that academic writers should be mindful of, including, inter alia, writing concisely, avoiding clumsy sentences, and consistency in my argument (Cleenewerch and Gulma 2024, 12-14). I would like to emphasize that producing books and articles is “the product of sustained reflection over a long period,” which entails multiple rounds of peer reviews and editing with amendments to reinforce the arguments put forward by the pertaining piece to countering back critiques received from peers.

b) Technical Aspects of Essay Writing

This section of the coursepack elaborates my findings while reading the relevant sections on using punctuation marks, diverse types of English, the Chicago Manual of Style, and Latin expressions.

i) Punctuation

First, the punctuation styles and rules may vary across different countries, e.g., American and English style (Cleenewerch and Gulma 2024, 23). In American English, double quotation marks (“”) are used for the primary quotation, while single quotation marks (‘’) are used for quotes inside the initial quotation. In British English, single quotation marks (‘’) are for the primary quotation, and double quotation marks (“”) are employed for quotes within it. Additionally, in American English, commas and periods are placed inside the quotation marks, whereas in British English, they are placed outside. This difference would be of paramount importance, especially when we attempt to submit to the press or journal in certain jurisdictions with the influence of American or British English.

ii) American vs British English

Chapter 3 provides detailed examples of how British and American English can be different from each other (Cleenewerch and Gulma 2024, 25). Even though the most commonly used style of English is American, it would be important to note that the dominant style of English is British in international dispute resolution, especially international arbitration. Given that my prior academic background is based in the United States, I should carefully be mindful of the differences between the British and American writing styles when making submissions in front of arbitral tribunals and submitting articles in established English journals.

iii) Chicago Manual of Style

Chapter 6 offers the general features of the Chicago Style Guide, including abbreviations, capitalization, compound words, italics, numbers, quotations, page formats, footnotes, headings & lists, endnotes, and bibliographies (Cleenewerch and Gulma 2024, 43-57). Amongst many details, I found the quotations and footnote sections very useful. I am more than willing to revisit this guide when I face uncertainties in formatting issues.

iv) Latin Abbreviations and Expression

Chapter 7 exhibits a table of Latin abbreviations and corresponding dictum that are frequently used in academic essay writings (Cleenewerch and Gulma 2024, 59-64). Using Latin maxims and abbreviations is also fairly common in legal submissions. The Latin maxims that I should have used more frequently are as follows:

a fortiori (with even stronger reason); a posteriori (from effects to causes; reasoning based on past experience); a priori (from causes to effects; conclusions drawn from assumptions; from what comes before; deductive reasoning); ex officio (out of one's duty or office); ex post facto (retrospectively); ipso facto (by the fact itself); non sequitur (it does not follow); quid pro quo (something in return); sic (thus used; thus spelt); vide (see); stat (as it was originally) (Cleenewerch and Gulma 2024, 62-64).

c) Plagiarism

Chapter 4 defines plagiarism as “*the writer us[ing] a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.*” Several resolutions, such as quotations and paraphrases, can be utilized to prevent plagiarizing by any chance (Cleenewerch and Gulma 2024, 36-37). However, quotations should not be abused, especially when the information is classified as “*common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas*” (Cleenewerch and Gulma 2024, 38). In addition, it would be essential to know from a sufficient degree of literature review that the writer’s opinion in the paper is not repeated in other publications.

d) Style Guide

There are various kinds of style guides adopted by multiple publishers, which may direct the writers to adopt the guidance on technical and substantial aspects (Cleenewerch and Gulma 2024). Indeed, as mentioned by authors, freelancer writers would highly benefit from utilizing style guides to develop their guides for potential readers (Cleenewerch and Gulma 2024).

There is no fixed style guide writing submission in international arbitration, as arbitrators may be based in various jurisdictions that offer different types of writing culture. Although commonwealth-qualified legal professionals are the majority, with the attempts to enhance diversity in this realm, the nationality of arbitrators now varies to a large extent. Thus, the participants in international dispute resolution weigh consistency over strict compliance with a specific style guide. However, to enhance certainty, some arbitrators issue procedural orders specifying their preferred style guide to follow by the parties when making submissions, which is often regarded as helpful.

3) CONCLUSION

This first session of ACA-401D was an excellent enlightenment for me, as I realized what else could be done to enhance my academic writing by identifying the deficiency in my knowledge. Technical aspects in essay writing are essential to maintain consistency, which makes the reader feel comfortable and focused on the content. With that in mind, I am eager to advance my writing skills by adopting those learned skills from the first session.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period I*. Fifth Edition. Washington D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.